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A dynamic *delta*-SPH model: how to get rid of diffusive parameter tuning

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Abstract

This work aims to clarify some of the dissipation properties observed in the weakly compressible SPH model with artificial diffusive terms, by specifically considering the δ -SPH formulation. The main features of the δ -SPH formulation are the use of two diffusive terms added in the continuity and momentum equations in order to stabilise the scheme. The action of the two artificial diffusive terms can be, in principle, arbitrarily tuned by two coefficients, namely δ and α . Thanks to the particular structure of the weakly-compressible SPH scheme it is possible to measure the energy dissipated by each term separately. Therefore, the effects on the dissipation process when changing δ and α are analysed. It is found that the two components are strictly related, and, surprisingly, different sets of coefficients lead in most of the cases to similar amount of total dissipated energy. Further, the results obtained by the δ -SPH formulation are compared with those obtained by a δ -LES-SPH. In the latter δ and α parameters are determined through a turbulence closure model and are, therefore, different for each particle. Within this new scheme the two parameters dynamically change depending on the local and instantaneous flow conditions and are no longer to be regarded as tunable parameters.

Key words: Smoothed Particle Hydrodynamics, Energy dissipation, δ -SPH, Dam-break flows, Free-surface flows, Water impacts, Large Eddy Simulation

1 Introduction

A fundamental aspect of interest in theoretical and applied sciences is the determination of the amount of energy dissipated during a certain physical process.

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To this aim, numerical tools are able to provide interesting insights about the complexity of the problems observed in nature, whose solution could be much more difficult by adopting a different approach. Among the various typologies of numerical methods, a relatively new class of solvers is based on the idea of treating the domain of calculation as a meshless scattered sets of points and has been successfully applied to solve various problems (see *e.g.* [1, 20, 21, 27, 10, 6]).

The Smoothed Particle Hydrodynamics (SPH) method is one of the most broadly used meshless Lagrangian method. Thanks to the particle approach, in SPH it is possible to easily evaluate the total energy of the system and, because of its explicit nature, to determine the temporal variations of its different components, such as potential, kinetic and internal energy. For example, a study in the context of the energy conservation in gravity wave evolution has been presented in [16] for non-breaking and in [13] for breaking waves. Beside the energy conservation, the SPH model is characterized also by interesting properties on the conservation of the circulation. In [2] this aspect is inspected in the context of breaking waves where circulation and vorticity are generated through the free-surface dynamics.

In the work by [23], the energy conservation properties are analysed for the Moving Particle Semi-implicit (MPS) and for the incompressible SPH model, being the two methods closely related [38]. A comparison of the energy evolution between weakly-compressible and incompressible solvers occurring during fluid impact problems has been studied by [29].

In the present work the focus is on the study of the energy dissipation properties of the δ -SPH when dealing with violent free-surface flows involving impacts and breaking wave dynamics. The δ -SPH model is a weakly-compressible SPH variant in which a diffusive term is added in the continuity equation together with an artificial viscous term which is present in the momentum equation. The magnitudes of the two terms is tuned through the parameters δ and α . A good combination of these two coefficients enhance the stability of the scheme.

The energy conservation properties of the δ -SPH model have been analysed in [5], in which it is shown that the density diffusive term acts as a supplementary dissipation acting predominantly on shock pressure waves. In the same work, the explicit expression for the amount of energy dissipated by the diffusive term is given, allowing for an exact quantification of the contributions related to artificial viscosity and density diffusion. After that, an energy analysis of the δ -SPH has been carried out for a problem involving moving solid boundaries [11] and successively applied to practical problems, regarding, for example, the determination of the amount of energy dissipated for a problem involving wave resonance in a gap [32].

A successive step in the understanding of the physical meaning of the δ -SPH model has been presented in the work by [18], in which it is shown that the SPH smoothing procedure can be actually regarded as a Large Eddy Simulation (LES) Lagrangian

filtering. In this way the δ -SPH model can be reinterpreted using turbulence closure models in which the magnitude of the viscous and density diffusion terms are determined by the local flow conditions for every time instant of the simulation, resulting in a dynamic evaluation of δ and α for each particle. The model, named δ -LES-SPH, has been then applied in [33] to analyse the energy balance occurring during the interaction between waves and structures.

The aim of the present work is to show that the two dissipation terms do not act independently, being strictly linked to each other. In order to get further insights the analyses are performed also under the perspective of the turbulence closure model. Indeed, the main difference between the two formulations is that, in the classical definition of the δ -SPH, the tuning coefficients for the diffusive terms are fixed at the beginning of the simulation and remain constant during the whole time evolution, while in the δ -LES-SPH model their values change dynamically on the base of the velocity gradients.

The effects of the choice of the parameters who determine the magnitude of the dissipation in the δ -SPH model (that is usually made arbitrarily within a certain range of values) are studied, and compared with the results obtained by the δ -LES-SPH model. On the base of the results from benchmark test-cases concerning free-surface flows, it is shown that the use of the δ -LES-SPH model allows for a better compromise between stability of the solution and low dissipation of the scheme.

The work is organised as follows:

- i) firstly, the governing equations are presented in section 2 and δ -SPH model is briefly recalled in section 3 along with the equations expressing the energy balance of the particle system;
- ii) in section 4 the equations of the δ -LES-SPH model are described;
- iii) section 5 is dedicated to a preliminary analysis using two different test-cases. This analysis shows how the energy dissipation mechanism varies in the δ -SPH model, when using different couples of values of δ and α ;
- iv) finally, in section 6, the analysis on the second benchmark of section 5 is repeated using the δ -LES-SPH scheme and the two outcomes are compared, highlighting some remarkable properties of the last scheme.

In the following, all the paragraphs which report important notes and results are highlighted through the symbol ► and using *italic* font.

2 Governing equations

The Navier-Stokes equations for a weakly-compressible and barotropic fluid can be written in a Lagrangian form as:

$$\begin{cases} \frac{D\rho}{Dt} = -\rho\nabla \cdot \mathbf{u}, & p = f(\rho), \\ \frac{D\mathbf{u}}{Dt} = \mathbf{g} - \frac{1}{\rho}\nabla p + \frac{1}{\rho}\nabla \cdot \mathbb{V}. \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

In system (1) ρ , \mathbf{g} and \mathbf{u} represent the density, the external volume forces and the velocity vectors, respectively. The quantity p is the pressure while \mathbb{V} is the viscous stress tensor that, in the case of a Newtonian fluid, can be rewritten as:

$$\mathbb{V} = \lambda \text{tr}(\mathbb{D})\mathbb{I} + 2\mu\mathbb{D}, \quad (2)$$

where \mathbb{D} is the strain rate tensor, $\mathbb{D} = (\nabla\mathbf{u} + \nabla\mathbf{u}^T)/2$, and \mathbb{I} the Kronecker tensor, while μ and λ are the dynamic and the bulk viscosity coefficients, respectively. The role played by these coefficients in the SPH framework has been recently discussed in [14].

The second equation in the first row of the system (1) represents the state equation for the pressure field. When simulating a liquid phase, a barotropic hypothesis can be made, and the pressure becomes just a function of the density field. Moreover, as a consequence of the weakly-compressible assumption, the density fluctuations are very small and a simple linearised version of the state equation can be adopted [28]:

$$p = c_0^2 (\rho - \rho_0), \quad (3)$$

in which c_0 is the speed of sound, assumed to be constant during the whole time evolution, and ρ_0 is the density at the free-surface. To guarantee a weakly-compressible regime the density fluctuations have to be confined to $1\%\rho_0$ [34]. This constrain results in a value for c_0 that is much lower than that of the real fluid, but much faster than the bulk velocity (resulting in a fair compromise between quality of the results and computational costs).

From the above consideration it results that the choice of c_0 is problem dependent, and needs to be set through a preliminary analysis of the flow to simulate. By defining a suitable reference velocity U_{ref} and the related Mach number as:

$$U_{\text{ref}} = \max\left(\|\mathbf{u}\|, \sqrt{\frac{p}{\rho}}\right), \quad \text{Ma} = \frac{U_{\text{ref}}}{c_0}, \quad (4)$$

it results that the weakly-compressible regime is guaranteed if $\text{Ma} \leq 0.1$ (see *e.g.* [5, 29]). During the simulation the relative variation of the density are monitored in order to check the validity of the above assumption.

► *It is important to note that the Ma number, in the context explained above, is not a free parameter and, as shown in the following, its range of variability is quite narrow as well as the other numerical parameters of the scheme. Indeed, the use of large c_0 (i.e. very low Mach number) not only increases the CPU costs because of the small time steps required but, as shown in section 3.2, it leads to higher dissipation.*

3 The δ -SPH model

In the δ -SPH model [4, 28] the governing equations (1) are discretized in the following form:

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \frac{D\rho_i}{Dt} = -\rho_i \sum_j (\mathbf{u}_j - \mathbf{u}_i) \cdot \nabla_i W_{ij} V_j + \delta h c_0 \sum_j \mathcal{D}_{ij} \cdot \nabla_i W_{ij} V_j, \\ \frac{D\mathbf{u}_i}{Dt} = \mathbf{g}_i - \frac{1}{\rho_i} \sum_j (p_i + p_j) \nabla_i W_{ij} V_j + \alpha h c_0 \frac{\rho_0}{\rho_i} \sum_j \pi_{ij} \nabla_i W_{ij} V_j, \\ \frac{D\mathbf{r}_i}{Dt} = \mathbf{u}_i, \quad p_i = c_0^2 (\rho_i - \rho_0). \end{array} \right. \quad (5)$$

In system (5), the quantities ρ_i , \mathbf{u}_i , p_i and \mathbf{r}_i are respectively the density, the velocity, the pressure and the position associated to the i -th particle whereas \mathbf{g}_i is the body force at the position \mathbf{r}_i . The particle volume V_i is a function of the particle mass m_i and density ρ_i . The kernel function is denoted with the term W_{ij} and the symbol ∇_i represents its gradient computed with respect to \mathbf{r}_i . In the present work a Wendland C2 kernel [41] with a cut-off radius set at $2h$ is adopted, where h is the smoothing length. A ratio $h/\Delta x = 2$ is chosen, where Δx represents the initial particle spacing.

The diffusive term, \mathcal{D}_{ij} , can be expressed in the following form:

$$\mathcal{D}_{ij} = 2 \left[(\rho_j - \rho_i) - \frac{1}{2} (\langle \nabla \rho \rangle_j^L + \langle \nabla \rho \rangle_i^L) \cdot (\mathbf{r}_j - \mathbf{r}_i) \right] \frac{(\mathbf{r}_j - \mathbf{r}_i)}{|\mathbf{r}_j - \mathbf{r}_i|^2}, \quad (6)$$

in which the quantity $\langle \nabla \rho \rangle_i^L$ represents the renormalized density gradient, as defined in [37]. The dimensionless parameter δ in system (5) defines the magnitude of the density diffusion. As demonstrated in [3], the range of variability of this parameter is very narrow and, therefore, is usually kept constant and equal to 0.1 [5, 31]. Note that, if $\delta = 0$, the system (5) becomes the standard SPH model.

The quantity π_{ij} in the viscous part of the momentum equation is defined as:

$$\pi_{ij} = \frac{(\mathbf{u}_j - \mathbf{u}_i) \cdot (\mathbf{r}_j - \mathbf{r}_i)}{(\mathbf{r}_j - \mathbf{r}_i)^2}. \quad (7)$$

The quantity α is the parameter for the artificial viscosity that is usually chosen in the range [0.01 - 0.05] for stability reasons.

In the problems considered in this work, since the geometry of the solid boundary is straightforward to be implemented (no curved boundaries are considered), classical ghost particles [15] are implemented for the modelling of the solid boundaries.

The solver employs a Runge-Kutta time integration scheme with a frozen diffusive approach (for more details see [3]). The time step is set using the following relation:

$$\Delta t = \text{CFL} \min_i \left(\frac{h}{c_0 + h \max_j \pi_{ij}} \right) \quad (8)$$

and the CFL is set equal to 1.5, which guarantees the stability of the scheme. The relation (8) is not comprehensive for low Reynolds number flows for which the constraint on the viscosity diffusion process shall also be taken into account. However, for the problems studied in this work the latter condition never applies.

► *As inspected in [5] and further shown in section 5, when using the δ -SPH scheme described above, the numerical dissipation linked to the time integration is always negligible for whatever value of α . This is not the case when using the standard SPH scheme (i.e. $\delta = 0$) for which the time integration errors depend on the α value and on the adopted time integrator (see e.g. [35, 5]). For this reason the standard SPH scheme is never considered in the present work.*

3.1 Energy conservation equations

Following the analysis by Antuono et al. [5], in the δ -SPH model the energy balance can be written as:

$$\frac{D\varepsilon_M}{Dt} + \frac{D\varepsilon_C}{Dt} = \mathcal{P}_\delta + \mathcal{P}_\alpha + \mathcal{P}_s. \quad (9)$$

In eq. (9), the quantity \mathcal{P}_s represents the power exchange at the interface solid/fluid. As shown by [5] this quantity is dependent on the technique adopted to model the solid boundary since it may be different from zero also in the case of non-moving solid boundaries. In the problems analysed in this work, since classical ghost particles are implemented and the boundaries are not moving, this quantity results to be negligible with the respect to the others power terms and therefore is not considered in the analyses of this work.

In the left side of eq. (9) the quantity ε_M represents the mechanical energy, that is equal to the sum of kinetic ε_K and potential ε_P energies. In the SPH framework these quantities can be evaluated through summations over the fluid particles:

$$\varepsilon_K = \sum_j \frac{1}{2} m_j \|\mathbf{u}_j\|^2, \quad \varepsilon_P = \varepsilon_P(y_0) + \sum_j m_j g y_j, \quad (10)$$

in which $\varepsilon_P(y_0)$ represents the potential energy at $y = 0$. In eq. (10) the summations are extended to all the fluid particles of the domain. The quantity ε_C is the elastic energy due to the possibility of the fluid particles to be compressed (as previously mentioned, coming from the weakly-compressibility assumption made for the fluid). This quantity represents therefore the reversible component of the internal energy that, if the linear state equation (5) is used, can be expressed as:

$$\varepsilon_C = \varepsilon_C(\rho_0) + c_0^2 \sum_j m_j \left[\log\left(\frac{\rho_j}{\rho_0}\right) + \frac{\rho_0}{\rho_j} - 1 \right], \quad (11)$$

in which $\varepsilon_C(\rho_0)$ is the elastic energy at rest conditions. In the right side of eq. (9) the dissipative components are represented. Specifically, the quantity \mathcal{P}_α is the power dissipated by the viscous component:

$$\mathcal{P}_\alpha = \alpha hc_0 \rho_0 \sum_i \sum_j \frac{\pi_{ij}}{2} (\mathbf{u}_i - \mathbf{u}_j) \cdot \nabla_i W_{ij} V_j V_i, \quad (12)$$

while \mathcal{P}_δ is the power dissipated by the diffusive term:

$$\mathcal{P}_\delta = \delta hc_0 \sum_i \frac{p_i}{\rho_i} \sum_j \mathcal{D}_{ij} \cdot \nabla_i W_{ij} V_j V_i. \quad (13)$$

Eq. (9) can be also presented in its integral form (after neglecting the term \mathcal{P}_s) as:

$$\Delta \varepsilon_M + \Delta \varepsilon_C = -Q, \quad (14)$$

in which $\Delta \varepsilon_M = \varepsilon_M - \varepsilon_{M0}$ and $\Delta \varepsilon_C = \varepsilon_C - \varepsilon_{C0}$ are the variations of mechanical and elastic energies in the interval $[t_0, t]$, and:

$$Q = Q_\alpha + Q_\delta = - \int_{t_0}^t \mathcal{P}_\alpha d\tau - \int_{t_0}^t \mathcal{P}_\delta d\tau \quad (15)$$

is the dissipated energy or, in other words, the mechanical energy transformed into heat in the same time interval. For the analyses performed in this work it is also useful to define the variation of internal energy of the fluid $\Delta \varepsilon_I = \Delta \varepsilon_C + Q$.

► *It has to be recalled that, while the closure of the equation (9) is intrinsically guaranteed by the δ -SPH scheme, the closure of the energy balance (14) using the definitions (10) and (11) depends on the time integration. In any case, as already mentioned, for the simulations presented in this work this error results to be always negligible when large enough values of δ are used (i.e. $\delta \sim 0.1$).*

3.2 Link between the α parameter and the Reynolds cell number

The magnitude of the artificial viscosity α can be linked to the real viscosity of the fluid. In fact, following *e.g.* [19], the equivalent dynamic viscosity as implemented

in system 5, is equal to:

$$\mu = \frac{\alpha h c_0 \rho_0}{K}, \quad (16)$$

where $K = 2(n+2)$ and n is the number of spatial dimensions of the problem. For a given value of α , c_0 and Δx (considering that $h/\Delta x$ has been set equal to 2) we can evaluate a Reynolds number Re as:

$$Re = \frac{\rho_0 U d}{\mu} = \left(\frac{Ma}{\alpha}\right) \left(\frac{d}{\Delta x}\right) \frac{K}{2} \stackrel{2D}{=} 4 \left(\frac{Ma}{\alpha}\right) \left(\frac{d}{\Delta x}\right), \quad (17)$$

where U and d are the reference velocity and length of the specific problem considered.

The Reynolds cell number $Re_{\Delta x}$ can be defined considering the spatial resolution $d/\Delta x$:

$$Re_{\Delta x} = \frac{\rho_0 U \Delta x}{\mu} = Re \left(\frac{\Delta x}{d}\right) = \left(\frac{Ma}{\alpha}\right) \frac{K}{2} \stackrel{2D}{=} 4 \left(\frac{Ma}{\alpha}\right). \quad (18)$$

The last relation is important since links α to $Re_{\Delta x}$. When $Re_{\Delta x} = O(1)$, all the main vorticity scales are resolved by the SPH model using the discretization $d/\Delta x$, which is in turn $O(Re)$. Generally, in most of the SPH simulations of free-surface flows, $Ma \sim 0.1$, hence $Re_{\Delta x} \sim 1$ implies α about 0.1. For example, the same test-case investigated in section 5.2 has been studied through a Direct Numerical Simulation (DNS) by [13] at $Re=1000$, with $d/\Delta x = 800$. In that case the Reynolds cell number was $Re_{\Delta x} = 1.25$ (*i.e.* $\alpha = 0.21$) and the authors showed that the results obtained, at the spatial resolution $d/\Delta x$ adopted, were practically not dependent anymore on the spatial discretization.

► *Considering liquids like water, the Reynolds number of interest in this work is around $10^5 - 10^6$, which implies a $d/\Delta x$ of order $10^5 - 10^6$ to perform a DNS. This constraint is prohibitive even in a 2D framework. Therefore, the usual compromise is to accept $Re_{\Delta x}$ of order 10 (*i.e.* $\alpha \sim 0.01$ and $Ma/\alpha \sim 10$) and, because the typical resolution is $d/\Delta x \sim 10^2 - 10^3$, it follows that the Re in the SPH simulations will be of order $10^3 - 10^4$. In such a condition ($Re_{\Delta x} \sim 10$), the smallest vortex scales are numerically damped and neither resolved nor modelled.*

► *It is worth noting that $\alpha = 0.01$ and $Ma = 0.1$ are the usual parameters adopted by SPH practitioners when performing inviscid simulations. We will show in section 5 that this choice of parameters corresponds to a specific condition for the two energy components Q_α and Q_δ . In particular we will show in a heuristic way that $Ma/\alpha = 10$ implies $Q_\alpha \sim Q_\delta$ when simulating violent free-surface flows.*

Another possibility, based on physical assumptions, is the use of a sub-particle scale model through the addition of an eddy viscosity, thus resulting in a Large Eddy Simulation (LES). In the latter, only the large vortex scales are directly solved while vortices smaller than the adopted spatial resolution Δx are modelled by the sub-grid

model under the assumption that the small scale turbulent motions are statistically isotropic. This approach is presented in section 4 with the δ -LES-SPH model, in which α and δ vary for each particle and are evaluated through a simple algebraic sub-grid model. Thanks to this, using high resolutions like $d/\Delta x \sim 10^3 - 10^4$, it is possible to increase the Reynolds number up to $10^4 - 10^5$.

The orders given in this section are just qualitative. Indeed, it is well known in the LES literature that the proper identification of the spatial resolution needed for a LES simulation, for a given flow at high Reynolds number, is problem dependent and requires an accurate analysis *a posteriori* of the solution (see *e.g.* [24, 42]). Furthermore, in a 3D framework the Kolmogorov length scale l is linked to the Reynolds number with the law $l/d \sim \text{Re}^{-3/4}$ while only in the 2D framework it follows $l/d \sim \text{Re}^{-1}$ (see *e.g.* [25]).

4 The δ -LES-SPH model

In the work presented by Di Mascio et al. [18], the SPH method has been revisited within a LES perspective. In that work the Lagrangian formulation of the LES is used to re-interpret the SPH approximation of differential operators as a specific model based on the decomposition of the LES filter into spatial and time filters. The derived equations represent a general LES-SPH scheme and contain terms that in part come from LES filtering and in part derive from SPH kernels. The obtained LES scheme is written in a fashion similar to the δ -SPH model (5), as:

$$\begin{cases} \frac{D\rho_i}{Dt} = -\rho_i \sum_j (\mathbf{u}_j - \mathbf{u}_i) \cdot \nabla_i W_{ij} V_j + hc_0 \sum_j \delta_{ij} \mathcal{D}_{ij} \cdot \nabla_i W_{ij} V_j, \\ \frac{D\mathbf{u}_i}{Dt} = \mathbf{g}_i - \frac{1}{\rho_i} \sum_j (p_i + p_j) \nabla_i W_{ij} V_j + hc_0 \frac{\rho_0}{\rho_i} \sum_j \alpha_{ij} \pi_{ij} \nabla_i W_{ij} V_j, \\ \frac{Dr_i}{Dt} = \mathbf{u}_i, \quad p_i = c_0^2 (\rho_i - \rho_0). \end{cases} \quad (19)$$

It is important to underline that in the expression given in system (19), compared with the original formulation given in [18], only the leading terms are considered. Regarding the continuity equation in system (19), in the δ -LES-SPH viewpoint the coefficient δ is not constant but it varies with the considered i -th and j -th interacting particles. According with [18], the quantity δ_{ij} is written as:

$$\delta_{ij} = 2 \frac{\delta_i \delta_j}{\delta_i + \delta_j}, \quad (20)$$

where:

$$\delta_i = \frac{v_i^\delta}{c_0 h}, \quad v_i^\delta = (C_\delta l_{LES})^2 \|\mathbb{D}\|_i, \quad (21)$$

in which C_δ is a constant equal to 1.5 and l_{LES} is a reference length for the SPH filtering procedure that here has been set equal to the radius of the kernel (*i.e.* $l_{LES} = 2h = 4\Delta x$). The value of the constant C_δ has been calibrated in [18] by simulating free decay turbulence in periodic domains in both 2D and 3D frameworks. The quantity $\|\mathbb{D}\|$ is given by:

$$\|\mathbb{D}\| = \sqrt{2\mathbb{D} : \mathbb{D}}, \quad (22)$$

where the strain-rate tensor is computed through the following formula:

$$\mathbb{D} = \frac{1}{2} \sum_j [(\mathbf{u}_j - \mathbf{u}_i) \otimes (\mathbb{L}_i \cdot \nabla W_{ij}) + (\mathbb{L}_i \cdot \nabla W_{ij}) \otimes (\mathbf{u}_j - \mathbf{u}_i)] V_j. \quad (23)$$

Analogously to the term δ_{ij} , also the viscous coefficient α_{ij} becomes a function of the i -th and j -th interacting particles and can be expressed in the following form:

$$\alpha_{ij} = \alpha + 2 \frac{\alpha_i \alpha_j}{\alpha_i + \alpha_j}, \quad (24)$$

where

$$\alpha = \frac{K \mu}{c_0 h \rho_0}, \quad \alpha_i = \frac{K v_i^T}{c_0 h}. \quad (25)$$

In eq. (24), α is the contribution due to the real viscosity (see eq. (16)), while the second term is the turbulent viscosity contribution, being the quantity v_i^T defined as:

$$v_i^T = (C_s l_{LES})^2 \|\mathbb{D}\|_i, \quad (26)$$

in which $C_s = 0.12$ is the Smagorinsky constant. The eqs. (21), (25) and (26) represent the closure of the δ -LES-SPH model.

When considering violent free-surface flows, $\|\mathbb{D}\|$ has a singular behaviour in the limit $h \rightarrow 0$, especially during impacts and can reach unlimited values; therefore, in order to avoid stability issues, the following limiters are used: $\alpha_i < 0.2$, $\delta_i < 0.2$. This limiters generally act just on interface particles and during the single time step when free surfaces are in contact. Further physical investigations on the injection of turbulence during water impacts are left for future works.

Regarding the equations for the conservation of energy for the SPH with sub-particle scale modelling, the eq. (9), with the same definitions given in section 3.1, still holds. In this case, only the viscous (eq. 12) and diffusive (eq. 13) dissipations have to be rewritten considering the variability of the coefficients, resulting in:

$$\mathcal{P}_\alpha = hc_0 \rho_0 \sum_i \sum_j \alpha_{ij} \frac{\pi_{ij}}{2} (\mathbf{u}_i - \mathbf{u}_j) \cdot \nabla_i W_{ij} V_j V_i \quad (27)$$

and

$$\mathcal{P}_\delta = hc_0 \sum_i \frac{p_i}{\rho_i} \sum_j \delta_{ij} \mathcal{D}_{ij} \cdot \nabla_i W_{ij} V_j V_i. \quad (28)$$

Incidentally, we note that the sub-particle scale model presented in this section resembles the models by Balsara [7] and Morris and Monaghan [36] developed in order to modify the α parameter of each particle, adapting it on the base of the local flow characteristics. In particular, these older models were written for astrophysical problems where α is increased around shock waves, to stabilise the scheme. Conversely, α is reduced in region of shear-flow to avoid unphysical spread of angular momentum in galactic disks. In Colagrossi and Landrini [15] the Balsara's model is modified introducing a dependency on $(\mathbb{D} : \mathbb{D})$ anticipating the choice made on the LES-SPH model presented in this section.

5 δ -SPH model: preliminary simulations on the interaction between α and δ terms

In this section the numerical results for the δ -SPH model are presented. The analysis is focused on the evolution of the energy components defined in section 3.1 and highlight some peculiar features of the dissipation mechanisms of this scheme. Then, the same analysis will be repeated in section 6 where the δ -LES-SPH model is adopted and the outcomes of the two models are compared and discussed.

Two test-cases are considered in present section:

- i) the first one regards the dynamics of a water patch entering a still water tank,
- ii) the second one is a dam-break flow in a confined domain.

For the first benchmark (sec. 5.1) the dynamics share similarity with the problem studied by Trivellato et al. [40], in which the SPH solution was compared with a Mixed Finite Element scheme based on the potential theory. This test case aims at studying the energy dissipation mechanisms mainly in flat impacts and gravity wave propagation.

Concerning the second test-case (sec. 5.2), the same problem has been already studied, as regards the effects of the spatial resolution in [28, 3], while the differences due to the use of a mono-phase and a two-phase model in the energy conservation have been studied in [30]. With respect to the first test case, in this problem, the flow evolution is much more violent with a wider energy cascade starting from a unique large breaking wave followed by several breaking events of different scales and shapes.

For both the test-cases the analysis firstly addresses the evolution of the different energy components and the total energy balance. Then, the simulations are repeated by changing the value of the α coefficient and keeping $\delta = 0.1$. Indeed, as mentioned in section 3, for stability reasons the range of variability of δ is quite narrow, therefore the attention is focused on the remaining free parameters of

eq. (17), that are: α , $d/\Delta x$. Notwithstanding that, it will be shown that the role played by δ , reflected by its dissipated energy Q_δ , is strongly related to the choice of α . Conversely, as explained in section 2, the Mach number is always problem dependent and needs to be set by an *a priori* analysis of the problem at hand.

As remarked in section 3, with $\delta = 0.1$ the errors linked with the time integration are negligible when time steps are evaluated through the eq. (8), regardless the value of α adopted.

5.1 Water patch entering a still water tank

The initial configuration of the problem is given in Fig. 1, in which the water tank, with length $L = 10d$, is initialised with a hydrostatic pressure distribution while the water patch presents null initial pressure and an initial vertical velocity $U_0 = 0.05 \sqrt{gd}$. The spatial resolution adopted in the numerical simulations is, for all the cases, $d/\Delta x = 100$. From a preliminary simulation, obtained using a reduced number of particles, it is found that the maximum velocity in the field during the evolution is about $U_{\text{ref}} = 1.25 \sqrt{gd}$. Therefore, in order to set the Mach number equal to 0.1, the adopted speed of sound is $c_0 = 12.5 \sqrt{gd}$. Using such a value, the density variations are always below 1% during the whole simulation.

The energy quantities here presented are normalised with respect to $\Delta \varepsilon_{M_{\text{tot}}} = \varepsilon_{M_0} - \varepsilon_{M_\infty}$, in which ε_{M_0} is the initial mechanical energy, while ε_{M_∞} is the mechanical energy obtained after the kinetic energy has been completely dissipated and the system assumes a static configuration. The water dynamics generated in this problem is that of a “quasi” standing wave, and the different stages of the evolution are accurately described in the following, through the analysis of the energy conservation.

Fig. 1. Fluid domain with boundaries for the water patch and the still water tank.

5.1.1 Time evolution of mechanical and internal energy components

Here, the water dynamics and the time evolution of the single energy components are analysed, by considering the case $\alpha = 0.01$. In Fig. 2 the first stages of the time evolution of potential, kinetic, compressible and dissipated energies are presented. Specifically, ε_{P0} is the initial potential energy, ε_{K0} is the initial kinetic energy due to the initial velocity U_0 of the patch, while ε_{C0} is the energy due to the initial compression of the the fluid particles.

As it is possible to observe, a continuous transfer between the potential energy and kinetic energy occurs, corresponding to the different stages of the wave evolution. Indeed, the time instants in which the potential energy is at its maximum, the kinetic energy is at its minimum and vice versa. These significant time instants are highlighted in Fig. 2 and the correspondent frames of the flow evolution, with the velocity field, are represented in Fig. 3. The left plots in Fig. 3 correspond to the time instants in which the kinetic energy is at its maximum. Conversely, the right plots correspond to the time instants in which the potential energy is at its maximum. As the wave evolves the amplitudes of the oscillations progressively decrease since the energy is dissipated, resulting in an increase of Q . Regarding the compressible energy only very small oscillations around zero can be observed, in accordance with the weakly-compressible assumption.

In Fig. 4 the time evolution of mechanical and internal energies is presented. The mechanical energy lost during the flow evolution is converted into internal energy. The resulting variation of total energy, $\Delta\varepsilon_{tot} = \Delta\varepsilon_M + \Delta\varepsilon_I$, is negligible during the flow evolution within an error of 0.3% of $\Delta\varepsilon_{Mtot}$. This variation is to be ascribed to the power dissipated at the solid/fluid interface \mathcal{P}_s and, to a lesser extent, in the time integration (see also [5] for further details about the accuracy of this energy

Fig. 2. Time evolution of kinetic, ε_K , potential, ε_P , compressible, ε_C , and dissipated, Q , energies for the water patch entering into the still water tank. The parameters used are $Ma = 0.10$, $d/\Delta x = 100$, $\delta = 0.1$, $\alpha = 0.01$.

Fig. 3. Frames of the simulation with velocity magnitudes for the time instants of the flow evolution highlighted in Fig. 2. The parameters used are $Ma = 0.10$, $d/\Delta x = 100$, $\delta = 0.1$, $\alpha = 0.01$.

balance).

A higher amount of energy is dissipated during the initial stage of the flow evolution, in which a more violent dynamics with breaking and cavities collapses takes place. After this initial part where the wave is attenuated at a fast rate,

Fig. 4. Time evolution of mechanical, ε_M , internal, ε_I , and total, ε_{tot} , energies for the water patch entering into the still water tank. The parameters used are $Ma = 0.10$, $d/\Delta x = 100$, $\delta = 0.1$, $\alpha = 0.01$.

the flow becomes practically irrotational and, thus, the dissipation rate becomes much smaller (but not null: as explained in [13] for viscous free-surface flow the dissipation is not driven only by the enstrophy but also by the free-surface motion itself). Therefore, a long time is required to completely dissipate the mechanical energy and reach the static condition. Indeed at the time instant $t\sqrt{g/d} = 140$ only about 55% $\Delta\varepsilon_{Mtot}$ is dissipated.

5.1.2 Analysis of the dissipative components for the δ -SPH

Here it is shown how the terms related to the viscous and density diffusive terms are involved in the dissipation of energy. To this purpose an analysis of the terms Q_α and Q_δ is presented considering different values for the parameter α . Specifically, four values of the artificial viscosity coefficient $\alpha = 0.0$, $\alpha = 0.01$, $\alpha = 0.02$ and $\alpha = 0.03$ are taken into account for these analyses.

The energy dissipated by the artificial viscosity term in the various cases is represented in Fig.5. As expected, the higher values of α result in higher amount of energy dissipated by the viscous term Q_α . The energy dissipated by the density diffusion Q_δ is presented instead in Fig. 6. In this case, it is interesting to notice that, although the δ coefficient is constant in all the cases, different results are obtained when the artificial viscosity coefficient is changed. Indeed, for the lower viscous dissipation case higher values of Q_δ are observed, whereas the case of a higher viscous dissipation results in a smaller dissipation by the density diffusion term. The energies dissipated by the two components compensate each other, resulting in a overall dissipation that remains about the same in the various cases. Remarkably, this behaviour is verified even for the case $\alpha = 0.0$, in which the energy is entirely

Fig. 5. Time evolution of the energy dissipated by the viscous term for the water patch problem. The parameters used are $Ma = 0.10$, $d/\Delta x = 100$, $\delta = 0.1$, for four different $\alpha = [0, 0.01, 0.02, 0.03]$.

Fig. 6. Time evolution of the energy dissipated by the diffusive term for the water patch problem. The parameters used are $Ma = 0.10$, $d/\Delta x = 100$, $\delta = 0.1$, for four different $\alpha = [0, 0.01, 0.02, 0.03]$.

dissipated by the density diffusive term. The comparison of the energy dissipated for the various values of the α coefficient is shown in Fig. 7 in which it is possible to see a time evolution of the simulations that is very close.

It is interesting also to notice that the energy dissipated by the density diffusion term (Fig. 6) presents a stair-like behaviour. This is due to the fact that, at the occurrence of an impact Q_δ suddenly increases while in the rest of the flow evolution the power dissipated by this term is very close to zero. A similar result has been obtained by [5], in which in presence of fluid impacts the high frequency oscillation of the pressure field (that are essentially acoustic waves generated after the impact) are smoothed by the action of the density diffusion term, leading to an increase of Q_δ .

Fig. 7. Time evolution of the total dissipated energy ($Q = Q_\alpha + Q_\delta$) for the water patch problem. The parameters used are $Ma = 0.10$, $d/\Delta x = 100$, $\delta = 0.1$, for four different $\alpha = [0, 0.01, 0.02, 0.03]$.

However, as highlighted in Figs. 5 and 6, also the artificial viscosity contributes to the total energy dissipation during impact stages. The two diffusive terms couple in a way such that the total amount of energy dissipated during the impact is practically the same for the different choices of α . This remarkable feature is studied more in details in the next section where a more complex flow and a larger range of parameters are considered. It is also worth noting that in the limit case with $\alpha = 0$ the energy is essentially dissipated during impact events and is approximately equal to the energy loss occurring in the other cases where $\alpha \neq 0$.

► *Summarising from this first test-case the following conclusions can be drawn:*

- a) *the energy balance is not affected by either the time integration or the solid boundary conditions (i.e. by the ghost particles approach);*
- b) *keeping $\delta = 0.1$, the dissipation Q_δ depends on the value of α ;*
- c) *keeping $\delta = 0.1$ and increasing α , the dissipation Q_α increases (as expected) while Q_δ reduces;*
- d) *the time evolution of the sum $Q_\delta + Q_\alpha$ (i.e. the total dissipation) seems to be not largely affected keeping $\delta = 0.1$ and varying α in the range $[0, 0.03]$;*
- e) *when using $\alpha = 0.01$ and $Ma = 0.1$, which are typical values used by SPH practitioners, $Q_\alpha \sim Q_\delta$;*
- f) *when using $\alpha = 0.03$, Q_δ is halved with respect Q_α and the time history of the Q , shown in Fig. 7, follows a path which starts deviating from the case with $\alpha = 0$.*

The last point suggests that with $\alpha = 0.03$ and $d/\Delta x = 100$ (i.e. $Re \approx 1060$, see eq. (17)) the viscous dissipation starts to become too large for simulating this test case. This will be further inspected in the next section where a second benchmark involving a more violent flow is analysed.

5.2 Dam-break flow impinging a vertical wall

In this section the energy analysis is used for the study of a dam-break flow in a confined domain. The problem was investigated experimentally by Buchner [8] and, more recently, by Lobovský et al. [26] and numerically by several authors (see *e.g.* [17, 15, 22, 28, 12, 30, 9]) becoming one of the most used benchmark for the SPH practitioners. The initial configuration of the problem is presented in Fig. 8, where the length of the tank is $L = 5.367d$.

Since in this second test-case a shallow water flow is considered, the reference velocity is $U_{\text{ref}} = \sqrt{gd}$. We start the analysis with a Mach number $\text{Ma} = \sqrt{gd}/c_0$ equal to 0.05, while in the next section the Ma number is doubled to $\text{Ma} = 0.1$ in order to check also the sensitivity of this parameter on the observed quantities.

For the plots shown in this section the resolution has been fixed to $d/\Delta x = 480$ varying the α parameter. In subsection 5.2.3 the effect of $d/\Delta x$ is also discussed. Using $\alpha = 0.01$ with the above spatial resolutions and Mach number, from the eq. (17), the Reynolds number simulated is of order 10^4 .

Conversely, the Reynolds number of the experiment by [8] is $\text{Re} = d\sqrt{gd}/\nu \simeq 1.5 \cdot 10^6$ which is too large to be resolved with Direct Numerical Simulation (DNS) as discussed in section 3.2. In fact, even using a Reynolds cell number $\text{Re}_{\Delta x} = \Delta x\sqrt{gd}/\nu = 10$, the resulting particle number would be $O(10^9)$ in 2D.

Therefore, one can approach this problem either by introducing the least possible numerical diffusion or by adding a model that introduces the dissipation occurring at the sub-particle scale, *e.g.* through the LES model introduced in section 4. Both these approaches are discussed in the following, highlighting the differences in terms of dissipation components.

Further, for the sake of simplicity, since the experimental Reynolds number is very high, a free-slip boundary condition is assumed. Indeed to enforce correctly a no-slip condition the Δx on the wall should verify $\text{Re}_{\Delta x} \sim O(1)$ implying also a very small time-step. In mesh-based solver this is achieved through mesh-stretching and

Fig. 8. Fluid domain with boundaries for the dam-break problem.

implicit time integration. It is well known that both these numerical techniques are not straightforward for the SPH model and are beyond the current state of the art.

The energy components are normalised with respect to $\Delta\varepsilon_{Mtot} = \varepsilon_{M0} - \varepsilon_{M\infty}$, that is the difference of potential energy between the initial and final configuration obtained when the kinetic energy is completely dissipated. The simulations have been run up to $t\sqrt{g/d} = 20.00$, that is the time for which about 90% of $\Delta\varepsilon_{Mtot}$ is dissipated.

5.2.1 Time evolution of mechanical and internal energy components

The water dynamics and the time evolution of the different energy components are analysed considering the case $\alpha = 0.01$ and $\delta = 0.1$. Using the relation (17) the Reynolds number is of order 10^4 . In Fig. 9 the evolution of kinetic, potential, dissipated and elastic energy components are displayed and some crucial time instants of the flow evolution are marked. The corresponding flow fields are presented in Figs. 10 and 11 in terms of total dissipated energy by each particle.

The initial kinetic energy ε_{K0} is null (the particles are initialised with zero velocities), while ε_{C0} is given by the initial compression of the fluid particles. As the mass of water starts to move, an increase of kinetic energy take place at the expense of the potential energy. This process continues until the fluid impacts the right wall, where the system increases again its potential energy, due to the uprising jet created after the impact against the vertical wall.

The first relative minimum/maximum in potential/kinetic energy is encountered at $t\sqrt{g/d} \cong 3.0$, as shown in Fig. 9 and displayed in the related frame in Fig.

Fig. 9. Time evolution of the various form of energy for the dam-break. In the plot are marked some significant instant of time, whose frames of simulation are displayed in Figs. 10 and 11. The parameters used are $Ma = 0.05$, $d/\Delta x = 480$, $\delta = 0.1$, $\alpha = 0.01$.

10. This stage ends at $t\sqrt{g/d} \cong 5.5$ when, as shown in Fig. 10, a plunging wave starts forming and the jet along the wall has reached its maximum height. The potential energy is again transformed into kinetic one, during the process of falling of the fluid mass and consequent wave breaking. As shown in top plots of Fig. 9 where contours of specific dissipated energy Q_i are plotted, up to this point the amount of dissipated energy is very small, the flow being essentially irrotational. A second relative minimum/maximum of potential/kinetic energy is then encountered at $t\sqrt{g/d} \cong 6.8$, as shown in Fig. 9. As displayed in the bottom frame of Fig. 10 the wave breaking generates a second jet which is followed by a several splash-up cycles. From this plot it is possible to see that during the impact the particles close impinging surfaces are affected by the diffusive terms and, after that, they are advected by the flow; this results in a cyan coloured line separating the two regions of the flow (the one of the plunging jet and the one underlying) in bottom plot of Fig. 10.

An interesting phenomenon occurs at $t\sqrt{g/d} \cong 8.5$, where the cavity generated after the wave breaking process collapses with a consequent fluid-fluid impact.

Fig. 10. Dam break problem: evolution of the dissipated energy field. The time instants shown are those represented in Fig. 9 where the different forms of energy are shown. The parameters used are $Ma = 0.05$, $d/\Delta x = 480$, $\delta = 0.1$, $\alpha = 0.01$.

Fig. 11. Dam break problem: evolution of the dissipated energy field. The time instants shown are those represented in Fig. 9 where the different forms of energy are shown. The parameters used are $Ma = 0.05$, $d/\Delta x = 480$, $\delta = 0.1$, $\alpha = 0.01$.

This rapid process creates an instantaneous compression of the fluid particles, that results in the peak in the elastic energy, as shown in Fig. 9. The compressible energy developed during the impact is then quickly dissipated, mainly due to the action of the diffusive terms, resulting in a sudden increase of internal energy (more details can be found in [29]). A second impact, with instantaneous accumulation of elastic energy is related to the impact of the second jet.

At the time instant $t\sqrt{g/d} \cong 9.3$ it can be seen that the fluid particles in the right part of the domain, subjected to the first impact, have dissipated a large amount of

Fig. 12. Time evolution of mechanical, ε_M , internal, ε_I , and total, ε_{tot} , energies for the dam-break problem. The parameters used are $Ma = 0.05$, $d/\Delta x = 480$, $\delta = 0.1$, $\alpha = 0.01$.

energy. After this time, another stage of the flow starts which is mainly driven by the vorticity evolution. In fact, after $t\sqrt{g/d} \cong 12.0$ the ricochet jets have lost most of their energy which has been transferred to vortical structures and to internal energy through impacts. A sloshing flow takes place in which the residual mechanical energy is dissipated through shear stress in vortexes and small local wave breakings. Indeed, as shown in bottom plot of Fig. 11, at $t\sqrt{g/d} \cong 15.5$ most of the fluid particles have been involved in dissipation processes and vortex structures are clearly visible. At this stage about 80% $\Delta\varepsilon_{Mtot}$ has been dissipated.

In Fig. 12 the conservation of the total energy of the system is reported. As also observed for the water patch test-case, the mechanical energy evolution is balanced by the internal energy (elastic energy and energy dissipated by diffusive terms), the error being below 0.5% of $\Delta\varepsilon_{Mtot}$.

5.2.2 Analysis of the dissipative components for the δ -SPH

In this section the analysis of the energy dissipation is presented. As done also in the previous section, dam-break simulations have been run with fixed particle resolution $d/\Delta x = 480$ and fixed value of $\delta = 0.1$, and using five different values of the artificial viscosity coefficient: $\alpha = [0.0, 0.005, 0.01, 0.02, 0.03]$. In Figs. 13 and 14 the evolution of the normalised energy components related to, respectively, artificial viscosity and density diffusion are shown for all the adopted values of α . As expected, in Fig. 13 the amount of energy dissipated through artificial viscosity grows as α becomes larger and, similarly to the previous test-case, the dissipation related to density diffusion decreases when α increases. Specifically, going towards $\alpha = 0$ even a slight difference of this parameter changes dramatically the evolution of Q_δ and Q_α (e.g. between $\alpha = 0.005$ and $\alpha = 0.0$).

Conversely to the first test-case, here for $\alpha = 0.01$, Q_α is already larger than Q_δ . However, this is not surprising if we consider that the Mach number for this benchmark is lower; indeed in the relation (17) it is the ratio Ma/α that set the viscosity level.

With respect to the water patch problem, in the dam-break case the impacts are more violent (*i.e.* larger mass and velocities are involved) and the amount of energy dissipated in those stages represents a large portion of the total energy. Further, in this problem it is also possible to observe the behaviour of the model when the dissipation is driven essentially by vorticity, that is, for $t\sqrt{g/d} > 12$. In particular it is interesting to note that in this last stage of the simulation for lower values of α the dissipation related to density diffusion becomes larger. The most interesting case is for $\alpha = 0$ in which a practically constant steepness of the curve is observed between $t\sqrt{g/d} = 12.0$ and $t\sqrt{g/d} = 20.0$. This is somewhat surprising as density diffusion is not expected to act in regions of the flow characterised by high velocity gradients.

This phenomenon can be better understood looking at the vorticity fields at the end of the simulation, $t\sqrt{g/d} = 20$ reported in Fig. 15. Higher values of α correspond to larger and less intense vortical structures as a consequence of the higher viscosity level. For $\alpha = 0.03$ the mechanical energy is essentially dissipated by the artificial viscous term. whereas for $\alpha = 0.005$ and $\alpha = 0.0$ the lower viscosity level allows the vorticity to distribute on a much wider range of vortex length scales. However, for $\alpha = 0$ the vorticity field clearly appears more noisy implying high frequency on the pressure field and, consequently, a more important role played by the density diffusion term.

Fig. 16 the evolution of the total dissipated energy Q is reported for the different values of α . Remarkably, the measured energies remain close to each other

Fig. 13. Dam break problem: time evolution of the dissipated energy related to artificial viscosity α . The parameters used are $Ma = 0.05$, $d/\Delta x = 480$, $\delta = 0.1$, for five different $\alpha = [0, 0.005, 0.01, 0.02, 0.03]$.

Fig. 14. Dam break problem: time evolution of the dissipated energy related to density diffusion δ . The parameters used are $Ma = 0.05$, $d/\Delta x = 480$, $\delta = 0.1$, for five different $\alpha = [0, 0.005, 0.01, 0.02, 0.03]$.

during the evolution and at $t\sqrt{g/d} = 20$ the maximum variation is about 5%. Thus, similarly to the water patch problem, the behaviours of the single energy components Q_δ and Q_α , which change considerably in the different cases, produce a total dissipation which is, at the end, not strongly influenced by this parameter. On the right plot of the same figure a logarithmic scale is used for the vertical axis in order to highlight the differences in the first stage of the evolution.

The results discussed in this section confirm that in order to resolve smaller vorticity scales at a given resolution $d/\Delta x$ one should limit α to very small values.

It has been shown also that if $\alpha \in (0, 0.01]$ is adopted, the noise in the numerical solution remains low without sensible variations on the total dissipated energy. On the other hand, using $\alpha > 0.01$ there are no noticeable benefits as the introduced viscosity results unnecessarily higher, resulting also in a quicker dissipation of the flow mechanical energy. On this ground, it is interesting to study if physically-based choice of α and δ , such as the one modelled by the LES-SPH scheme described in section 4, represents a good candidate for an alternative model.

► *From the second test-case we can confirm some of the results obtained for the first benchmark (see section 5.1). In particular:*

- a) *keeping $\delta = 0.1$ and using a ratio $Ma/\alpha \simeq 10$ one obtains $Q_\delta \sim Q_\alpha$;*
- b) *keeping $\delta = 0.1$ and varying $\alpha \in [0 - 0.03]$ the effect on the the time evolution of the total dissipation Q is limited;*
- c) *when using $\alpha = 0.03$, Q_δ is three time lower than Q_α and the time history of the Q , shown in Fig. 16, follows a path which starts deviating from the case with $\alpha = 0$.*

Furthermore, from the analysis of the vorticity fields we get:

Fig. 15. Dam break problem: vorticity fields at $t\sqrt{g/d} = 20$. The parameters used are $Ma = 0.05$, $d/\Delta x = 480$, $\delta = 0.1$. Five different $\alpha = [0, 0.005, 0.01, 0.02, 0.03]$ (from top to bottom) have been used.

- e) even if the total dissipation Q seems to be almost unaffected by the change of α , the vorticity fields are very different in terms of vortical structures scales resolved. This is an indication that almost the same quantities of the mechanical energy are distributed on different scales. This can be linked to the 2D framework and to the intense back scattering from the smaller eddies to the larger ones. This should not be the case in 3D, but this analysis is left for future works;
- f) for $\alpha = 0.0$ the vorticity field is characterised by a wider range of vortical scales; however, the field appears also more noisy with respect to the other cases (i.e. $\alpha > 0$). This is an indication that the δ -SPH scheme may be not

Fig. 16. Dam break problem: time evolution of the total dissipated energy. The parameters used are $Ma = 0.05$, $d/\Delta x = 480$, $\delta = 0.1$, for five different $\alpha = [0, 0.005, 0.01, 0.02, 0.03]$. Right plot: logarithmic scale is used on the vertical axis.

stable enough using just $\delta \neq 0$ and $\alpha = 0$. In order to achieve a vorticity spectrum similar to the latter, but free of noise, one should increase the spatial resolution whilst introducing a small value of α (i.e. $\alpha \sim 0.01$) as described in the next section.

5.2.3 Effect of the spatial resolution on the energy balance

Fig. 17 shows the vorticity field obtained for the four resolutions $d/\Delta x = 100, 200, 400$ and 800 . For this section the Mach number is increased to $Ma = 0.1$ and α is set equal to 0.01 while δ is fixed equal to 0.1 , as in the previous sections. As expected, and already shown by [28], increasing the spatial resolution $d/\Delta x$ more and more vortex scales will be generated during the post-breaking stage.

The effect on the vorticity field of $d/\Delta x$ resembles the one of α discussed in section 5.2.2. Considering the relation (17) this is not surprising considering that both the parameters α and $d/\Delta x$ set the viscosity level of the simulation. Beside this similarity, when looking to the energy balance the behaviours are different with respect to section 5.2.2, since the change of $d/\Delta x$ affects both Q_α and Q_δ . The plots in Fig. 18 shows that $d/\Delta x$ has a small influence on this dissipation, even if for the lowest resolution the curves slightly deviate from the other three. Further, Fig. 19 shows that, similarly to the α parameter in the previous section, also $d/\Delta x$ has not a large influence on the total energy dissipation Q (at least in the parameter ranges investigated). In the right plot of the same figure a logarithmic scale is used on the vertical axis in order to highlight the variations induced by the spatial resolution.

► *The relevant result from the analysis of the effect of $d/\Delta x$ is that for $Ma/\alpha = 10$ again it is found that $Q_\alpha \sim Q_\delta$. This result seems to be not affected by $d/\Delta x$.*

Fig. 17. Dam break problem: vorticity fields at $t\sqrt{g/d} = 20$ for $\delta = 0.1$, $\alpha = 0.01$, $\text{Ma} = 0.1$ and (from top to bottom) $d/\Delta x = \{100, 200, 400, 800\}$.

6 Numerical simulations using the δ -LES-SPH model

For the second benchmark, regarding the dam-break problem, the δ -LES-SPH model discussed in section 4 is also adopted. We note that using this scheme the errors on the energy balance due the time integration are, again, negligible. In this section we consider a Reynolds number $\text{Re} = 10^6$ and spatial resolution in the range

Fig. 18. Dam break problem: time evolution of the dissipated energy related to artificial viscosity Q_α and to the density diffusion Q_δ , for different values of $d/\Delta x$, ($\delta = 0.1, \text{Ma} = 0.1, \alpha = 0.01$).

Fig. 19. Dam break problem: time evolution of the total dissipated energy for different values of $d/\Delta x$, ($\delta = 0.1, \text{Ma} = 0.1, \alpha = 0.01$). Right plot: logarithmic scale is used on the vertical axis.

$d/\Delta x \in [100, 1600]$. This means that, using relation (17), the α parameter linked to the real viscosity is $O(10^{-5}) - O(10^{-4})$. With the above numbers it follows that:

- (i) in practice the dissipation is only given by the LES model, the diffusion due to physical viscosity being negligible;
- (ii) the spatial resolutions are too low for performing a suitable LES simulation: some relevant large eddy structures will be numerically damped and not resolved.

In such condition the LES model can be seen as an optimal non-tunable numerical

dissipation model for stabilizing the scheme. Indeed, within the δ -LES-SPH model the local δ_i and α_i act only in regions of the flow characterized by high velocity gradients. The discussion in the following is focused on the dissipative properties of this model. In the Appendix a short comparison of the pressure fields obtained through δ -LES-SPH and δ -SPH models is provided. This section is subdivided in two subsections:

- (6.1) in the first the Mach number and the spatial resolution are respectively set equal to $Ma = 0.05$, $d/\Delta x = 480$, as in the previous section 5.2, with such combination we obtain that $Q_\delta \sim Q_\alpha$;
- (6.2) in the second section, similarly to section 5.2.3, the analysis of the time evolution of the energy components are analysed varying the spatial resolution $d/\Delta x$ from 100 up to 1600 fixing the Mach number to 0.1.

6.1 Simulation at $Re=10^6$ using $Ma=0.05$ and $d/\Delta x = 480$

We start the analysis regarding the δ -LES-SPH model with a first test where the Mach number and the spatial resolution are set equal to the ones adopted in the previous section 5.2. In Fig. 20 the contour plot of α_i and δ_i are plotted at time instant $t\sqrt{g/d} = 12$, where violent impacts take place and the dissipative terms act mainly at the free-surface reconnections and around vortexes generated by breaking events.

In most of the fluid domain both α_i and δ_i are very close to zero. As described in section 4, both diffusive parameters are proportional to $\|\mathbb{D}\|$ and, thus, share the same spatial distribution. The values $\alpha = 0.01$, $\delta = 0.2$ are reached as maximum values just in the most critical regions of the fluid domain while the averaged values in the whole domain are $\bar{\alpha} = 0.002$, $\bar{\delta} = 0.04$.

Beside the above results, a surprising outcome can be found in Fig. 21, where the time evolution of Q_δ , Q_α and total dissipated energy obtained with δ -LES-SPH model are reported; from this plot it is clear that $Q_\delta \sim Q_\alpha$. Moreover, the time

Fig. 20. Dam break problem: contour plot of the α_i and δ_i fields obtained with the δ -LES-SPH model at time instant $t\sqrt{g/d} = 12$. The parameters used are $Ma = 0.05$, $d/\Delta x = 480$.

Fig. 21. Dam break problem $Re = 10^6$: time evolution of the total dissipated energy $Q_\delta + Q_\alpha$ and of single components Q_δ and Q_α for the δ -LES-SPH model. The parameters used are $Ma = 0.05$, $d/\Delta x = 480$.

Fig. 22. Dam break problem $Re = 10^6$: time evolution of the total dissipated energy for the LES-SPH model and for the δ -SPH model with $\alpha = 0.0$ and $\alpha = 0.01$. For all the three simulation $d/\Delta x = 480$ and $Ma = 0.05$ while for δ -SPH model the δ parameter is set equal to 0.1. Right plot: logarithmic scale is used on the vertical axis.

histories of Q_δ and Q_α are quite close to the ones shown in section 5.2 when setting $\alpha = 0.005$, $\delta = 0.1$ ($Ma = 0.05$, $d/\Delta x = 480$).

In Fig. 22 the total energy obtained with the LES-SPH model is compared to the δ -SPH model with $\alpha = 0.0$ and $\alpha = 0.01$. The LES-SPH line is very close to the one at $\alpha = 0.0$ up to about $t \sqrt{g/d} = 12$. This means that the dissipation processes are similar in this part of the flow which is dominated by violent impacts and intense splashing. Then, because of the large vorticity produced, the dissipation becomes more intense with respect to the other two cases, remaining however close to them.

Even if the dissipation processes are similar for the δ -LES-SPH and δ -SPH when

using the above parameters, differences appear when looking at the vorticity field at $t\sqrt{g/d} = 20$ (Fig. 23). The vorticity field with the δ -LES-SPH is similar to the one obtained with $\alpha = 0$ (see Fig. 15). However, the δ -LES-SPH is able to produce a less noisy field. This result is due to the spatial variation of the δ_i and α_i parameters which reduce the numerical dissipation in regions characterized by low velocity gradients.

Fig. 23. Dam break problem $Re = 10^6$: vorticity fields for the LES-SPH model at $t\sqrt{g/d} = 20.0$ with resolution $d/\Delta x = 480$

► *From this subsection the conclusions are:*

- a) *when the subgrid model dominates the viscous dissipation, the mechanical energy decay behaviour obtained by δ -LES-SPH model remains close to the one obtained by the simpler δ -SPH. In particular it is found that $Q_\delta \sim Q_\alpha$, similarly to what obtained with $Ma/\alpha \simeq 10$ and $\delta = 0.1$ in the δ -SPH;*
- b) *conversely, through the δ -LES-SPH model the vorticity distribution appears similar to the one obtained by δ -SPH with $\alpha = 0$ but it is less affected by numerical noise;*

6.2 Simulations at $Re = 10^6$ varying the spatial resolution from $d/\Delta x = 100$ up to $d/\Delta x = 1600$

Similarly to the analysis performed in section 5.2.3 for the δ -SPH model, here the results obtained with δ -LES-SPH, when changing the spatial resolution, are discussed. Fig. 24 shows the vorticity field for five different resolutions $d/\Delta x$, namely: 100, 200, 400, 800 and 1600. The last resolution correspond to a number of particles equal to 5,120,000. With such a discretization, a time evolution of $t\sqrt{g/d} = 20$ needs 214,000 time iterations corresponding to a CPU cost of 4 days on 96 cores (8 nodes with 12 cores Intel© Xeon© CPU E5-2620 v2 @ 2.10GHz each). As shown in the bottom plot of Fig. 24, it is clear that, even at this high resolution, not all the large eddies are resolved (this fact will be more evident at the end of this section). Indeed, comparing the vorticity fields at $d/\Delta x = 800$ and at $d/\Delta x = 1600$, large differences on the vorticity distribution exist.

Plots of Figs. 25 and 26 show the single components of the dissipation Q_α and Q_δ and the total dissipation Q for the five different resolutions. In all the cases the curves remain close to each other, similarly to what observed using the simple

Fig. 24. Dam break problem $Re = 10^6$: vorticity fields for the LES-SPH model at $t\sqrt{g/d} = 20$ varying the spatial resolution $d/\Delta x$. See supplementary material for the complete evolution of the finest simulation.

δ -SPH model in section 5.2.3. Again, we observe that $Q_\alpha \sim Q_\delta$, recovering the behaviour observed for $Ma/\alpha = 10$. In the right plot of Fig. 26 the evolution of total dissipated energy is reported using the logarithmic scale for the y-axis. This plot allows to better observe the initial evolution of Q which, differently from the late stages, converges as the resolution increases.

Finally, in order to quantitatively assess the role played by the δ -LES-SPH model, in Fig. 27 the evolution of the non-dimensional dissipated energy due to enstrophy

Q_ω is reported. The latter is defined as:

$$Q_\omega = \mu \int_0^t \int_\Omega \omega^2 dV \quad (29)$$

where Ω is the fluid domain.

In [13] it has been shown that in the dam break problem a large portion of the total viscous dissipation is due to this term when all the viscous scales are resolved. Conversely, as shown in Fig. 27, in the present case Q_ω remains always below

Fig. 25. Dam break problem $Re = 10^6$: time evolution of the dissipated energy related to artificial viscosity Q_α (left plot) and to the density diffusion Q_δ (right plot), for different values of $d/\Delta x$ and $Ma = 0.1$.

Fig. 26. Dam break problem $Re = 10^6$: time evolution of the total dissipated energy for different values of $d/\Delta x$ and $Ma = 0.1$; on the right plot a logarithmic scale is used for the vertical axis.

Fig. 27. Dam break problem $Re = 10^6$: time evolution of the dissipated energy component Q_ω for different values of $d/\Delta x$, ($Ma = 0.1$).

$0.01\Delta\varepsilon_{Mtot}$. This means that the resolved part of the viscous dissipation, which is related to the real viscosity μ , is negligible with respect to the modelled one, which is proportional to the turbulent viscosity. Moreover, increasing the resolution no convergence of Q_ω is observed. This represents a quantitative confirmation of the fact that, even for the highest resolution, the simulation is far from resolving the main vorticity scales. As a consequence, the observed dissipation is purely numerical, even if mimicking a physical behaviour. Further, the larger values of Q_ω observed for the higher resolutions confirm that the vorticity covers a larger range of scales with respect to coarser resolutions, since the beginning of the simulation.

Conclusions

An analysis of the energy dissipation for the weakly-compressible SPH scheme with diffusive terms has been presented. The investigation is based on the δ -SPH model, where the total amount of dissipated energy has been studied by looking at its main components, namely dissipation due to artificial viscosity, Q_α and due to density diffusion, Q_δ . Those components are studied fixing the parameter δ to 0.1 and changing the coefficient α and the particle resolution. Thanks to the stability properties of the δ -SPH scheme, the errors in the time integration were always negligible for whatever value of the α parameter, ensuring the closure of the total energy balance.

Regarding the numerical simulations performed, two test cases concerning free-surface flows have been adopted: a water patch entering in still water and a dam-break flow confined in a tank. The study has highlighted some relevant properties of the energy dissipation mechanisms in the δ -SPH model:

- i) keeping $\delta = 0.1$, the dissipation Q_δ depends on the value of α and, in particular, increasing α , the dissipation Q_α increases (as expected) while Q_δ reduces;
- ii) as a consequence, it is observed that the time evolution of the sum $Q_\delta + Q_\alpha$ (*i.e.* the total dissipation) is weakly dependent on the choice of α in the range

- [0, 0.03];
- iii) although the energy content is similar, the vorticity distributes at different length scales: the smaller the α , the larger the vorticity scale range, the case $\alpha = 0$ having the largest one (but affected by high numerical noise);
 - iv) when using $Ma/\alpha \simeq 10$, which is a typical choice of SPH practitioners, the energy dissipated by density diffusion and artificial viscosity are very close, $Q_\delta \sim Q_\alpha$, even varying the particle discretization.

The results of the δ -SPH model have been compared with those obtained from a SPH with sub-particle scale modelling, the δ -LES-SPH. In the latter the parameters of the diffusive terms are not arbitrarily defined but dynamically evaluated basing on the local and instantaneous flow characteristics. It is found that, when the subgrid model dominates the viscous dissipation (*i.e.* values of the real viscosity too low for the adopted resolution), the behaviour of the dissipated energy components obtained by the δ -LES-SPH model is similar to the one obtained by the simpler δ -SPH with $Ma/\alpha \simeq 10$. From this standpoint the LES model can be seen as an “optimal non-tunable” numerical dissipation model for stabilizing the scheme which act only in regions of the flow characterized by high velocity gradients. As a second result we found that, in the simulations obtained by the δ -LES-SPH model, the vorticity distribution appears similar to the one obtained by δ -SPH with $\alpha = 0$ but they are less affected by numerical noise.

Future works will address the properties of the δ -LES-SPH model in the 3D framework for which a different behaviour is to be expected and possible extensions of the present model by adding a Particle Shifting Technique (see, *e.g.*, [39]).

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Appendix

In this section the pressure fields obtained through the δ -SPH and δ -LES-SPH models are compared with the purpose of showing that the δ -LES-SPH is as efficient as the δ -SPH in removing high-frequency noise. In Fig. 28 the pressure

fields for both δ -LES-SPH and δ -SPH at $t\sqrt{g/d} = 6.15$ are reported for $d/\Delta x = 800$.

Small local differences are visible since the δ -SPH is slightly more dissipative, that implies an anticipation of the plunging jet impact (see [15] for more details). Consequently, the two flow evolutions present time lags in the acoustic wave trains. Beside this, the quality of the pressure fields is essentially the same.

In Fig. 29 the pressure recorded at probe P1 located at the right-bottom corner (see Fig. 28) is plotted for both cases. The two signals coincide up to $t\sqrt{g/d} = 6.15$, that is, when the plunging jet impinges the free surface. After this time, shifting in the acoustic waves propagation occur in the two simulation, as discussed above. Hence, the two signals do not overlap any more due to the different evolutions. However, the frequency contents of the two signal remain quite close, without numerical high-frequency spurious components. In Fig. 29 the numerical results are also compared with the experimental measurement by Lobovský et al. [26]. Even if the numerical outputs are quite close with the experimental data, discrepancies are quite visible and are related to the three-dimensionality of the real flow and to the air entrapment after time $t\sqrt{g/d} = 6$.

Fig. 28. Dam break problem: pressure field at time $t\sqrt{g/d} = 6.15$ using $Ma = 0.10$ and $d/\Delta x = 800$. Left: δ -LES-SPH model. Right: δ -SPH model using $\delta = 0.1$ and $\alpha = 0.01$. P_1 indicates the position of one of the pressure probes used in the experiments of [26].

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Fig. 29. Dam break problem: pressure time histories recorded by the probe P_1 (see Fig. 28). The experimental data of [26] are compared with the outputs of the δ -LES-SPH model and of the δ -SPH model ($\delta = 0.1$ and $\alpha = 0.01$). The Mach number of the simulation is $Ma = 0.10$ while spatial resolution adopted is $d/\Delta x = 800$.

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